
Awareness Article

Habitat, dietary preferences, foraging strategies and conservation measures of Indian Pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata* Gray, 1827): A conservation & awareness approach

Sweta Mishra^{1*}, Niraj Kumar² and Sanjeet Kumar¹

¹Ambika Prasad Research Foundation, Odisha, India

²Department of Zoology, Laxmi Narain Dubey College, Motihari, East Champaran, India

*Email-id: swetamishra.rdwu@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2213-0370>

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Abstract: The Indian Pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata* Gray, 1827) is a unique and endangered species facing severe threats from habitat loss, poaching, and trafficking. The population of these small mammals has declined in the wild due to indiscriminate poaching, illegal trade of live pangolins and their body parts, and habitat loss to a certain extent. Present study aims to address the habitat, dietary preferences, foraging strategies, and conservation measures of the Indian Pangolin. Present study reveals that the species inhabits a variety of habitats, including forests, grasslands, and scrublands. They feed on a diverse range of ants and termites. Authors also observed that the pangolin's foraging strategy is primarily nocturnal and solitary. To conserve this species, authors propose a multi-faceted approach that includes habitat protection, anti-poaching efforts, education and awareness programs, and community-based conservation initiatives. The study highlights the urgent need for conservation action to protect the Indian Pangolin and its habitats, and emphasizes the importance of raising awareness about the plight of this unique and fascinating species.

Keywords: Awareness, conservation, endangered, food habits, mammals, wildlife

Introduction

Pangolins, the scaly anteater, are nocturnal toothless mammals, with a streamlined elongated body covered with overlapping scales except the ventral surface (Aktins, 2004). They are insectivorous and inhabit tropical and subtropical forests, dry woodlands, and open savannah regions in Africa and Asia (Hutton, 1949). The French name "Pangolin" is derived from the Malayan word, "pengguling", which refers to the animal's unique defensive posture of rolling up into a tight ball (PEK, 2019). They are found throughout India except upper Himalayas, extreme Northeast, and some parts of the Thar desert.

Globally, there are eight extant species of pangolin. Genus *Manis* for Asian pangolins and *Phataginus* & *Smutsia* for African pangolins. Four species occur in Asia (*Manis pentadactyla*, *Manis crassicaudata*, *Manis culionensis* and *Manis javanica*) and the remaining four (*Smutsia temminckii*, *Smutsia gigantea*, *Phataginus tricuspis*, *Phataginus tetradactyla*) are found in Africa (Emry, 1970; Mahmood et al., 2014). In India, we have two species of pangolins that are *Manis crassicaudata* (Indian pangolin) and *Manis pentadactyla* (Chinese pangolin). Indian pangolins are found in Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Jharkhand, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Chhattisgarh, Rajasthan, Gujarat and West Bengal whereas Chinese pangolins are found in Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim and Tripura. Both species are protected in India as Schedule I species under the Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 and included in Appendix I of CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora). In Odisha, Indian pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) is reported from every district but due to many anthropogenic threats, including habitat degradation, habitat loss, biological invasions, overexploitation, pollution, and climate change the population is decreasing day by day and now Indian pangolins are stated Endangered in IUCN Red list (Qasim et al., 2024). This paper aims to study the habitat and food of the Indian pangolin and to develop effective conservation strategies to protect this endangered species from extinction.

Figure 1: An adult Indian pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*)

Morphological features

M. crassicaudata old world anteater, is a solitary medium-sized mammal with no teeth, external ear, a conical head, and a long-sticky tongue to lap up prey (Macdonald, 2006; Figure 1). It has an elongated body and tail covered with large overlapping keratinous scales, absent on the ventral side of the body, head, inner surfaces of limbs, and foot pads. The weight of an adult Indian pangolin may be between 8 to 16 kg and can measure up to 148 cm in length (Kaspal, 2010). The colour of scales varies from shades of brown to yellow, and sometimes it depends on the colour of the soil associated with the habitat of the pangolin. Unlike most mammals, hair is virtually absent on pangolins' dorsal surface except for thick, short hair between scales. However, thin, light-colored hairs are underneath the bare parts (Kotagama and Goonatilake, 2013). The tail can represent 39–54% of the total body length. The terminal scale on the ventral side of the prehensile tail is the key identifying feature of the Indian pangolin. Their large forelegs have long-sharp claws that aid them in digging the burrow and excavating

the insect's nest (Payne and Francis 1998). Indian pangolin is a nocturnal species so they primarily rely on their sense of smell to locate the nests of insect nests (Mohapatra and Panda, 2014). They are sexually dimorphic, and an adult male is much larger and heavier than a female of the same age (Perera et al., 2017; PEK, 2019).

Habitat of Indian Pangolin

The Indian pangolin occupies diverse habitats in its geographical range, and an understanding of its habitat characteristics, habitat preferences, and habitat utilization patterns in different environments is vital for conservation planning. Indian pangolins prefer to live in open and grasslands scrub forests, rainforests, tropical forests, moist forests, dry deciduous, wet forests, semi-evergreen forests, and near human settlements they also live in desert zones. The species is thought to adapt well to human-dominated landscapes and modified habitats such as plantations, farmlands, and near forest fringes (Roberts, 1977; Saxena, 1986; ZSI, 2002). The habitat preference of Indian pangolins tends to be specifically associated with certain tree or shrub species such as *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Acacia nilotica*, *Prosopis cineraria*, *Lantana camara* and *Ziziphus nummularia* (Mahmood et al., 2014). To survive, they must have minimal habitat requirements, such as an annual water supply for drinking, loose earth substrate for digging burrows, and an abundant food population (Pabasara et al., 2015). Many sightings and rescue records have also shown its presence in and around urban forests (Baillie et al., 2014). Indian pangolins dig two kinds of burrows, one for living and another for feeding. The presence of prey items and fecal matter, along with burrow depth and diameter, are considered important parameters for distinguishing the two types of burrows (Mahmood et al., 2013; Irshad et al., 2015). After a few months of using their shelter, Indian pangolins usually move on to dig a new one, probably within their home range which often overlaps with the distribution and abundance of its prey. Within the same year, it is possible to reoccupy an older living burrow (Mahmood et al., 2013). As a nocturnal animal, pangolins sleep curled inside their living burrow. Burrows are usually made under large rock boulders or sometimes in tree bases. Compared to living burrows, feeding burrows are considerably shallower (often less than 1m) and have smaller openings (Pabasara et al., 2015; Perera et al., 2017).

Dietary habits of Indian Pangolin

Ants and termites are preferred food sources for Indian pangolins. One of the Indian pangolin's preferred foods (Mahmood et al., 2013) is the red weaver ant (*Oecophylla smaragdina*, Figure 2). Two kinds of black ants were discovered by Irshad et al. (2015), including two termite species, *Camponotus confucii* and *Camponotus compressus*, as well as one called the primary food source for pangolins in Pakistan is *Odontotermis obesus*. The study revealed that the faces contained the most grit; the ants that ate were *Monomorium* sp., *Camponotus* sp. *Anoplolepis* sp. and *Oecophylla* species. The termites of the genus *Odontotermes* including *O. horni* and *O. redemanni* were also observed. Additionally, the body segments of insects, the exoskeleton of a juvenile scorpion, and the juvenile lacewing were observed (Karawita et al., 2020; Ramakrishna, 2024). In Nilgiris, the diet consisted of black ants, beetle wing sheath, cockroaches' remains and worms' skins (Hutton, 1949). Analyzing stomach contents is the basis for understanding the Indian pangolin's diet in India.

Figure 2: Habitat of red weaver ant (*Oecophylla smaragdina*)

The study of female Indian pangolin gut content in Waynad indicated that its diet was solely composed of *Leptogenys* sp. with a probable preference for ant eggs over adult ants and had high grit content (Ram et al., 2022). In captivity at the Nandankanan Biological Park, the Indian pangolin's showed acceptance for *Oecophylla smaragdina* and their eggs (Mohapatra and Panda, 2014). Ram et al., 2022 studied the Indian pangolin's diet in the tropical dry deciduous forest of Gir National Park in Western India and found a total of fifteen species of ants were observed in the diet of the Indian pangolin. These include two unidentified species of *Camponotus*, *C. compressus*, *C. angusticollis*, *Tetraponera rufonigra*, *T. allaborans*, *Dorylus labiatus*, one species of *Crematogaster*, one species of *Myrmicaria*, two species of *Lophomyrmex*, two species of *Pheidole* and two species of *Monomorium*. Among these, *C. compressus* was the most frequently observed species in the insect matter. The primary cause of concern has been reported to be the inability to understand and replicate the dietary requirements of Indian pangolins in captivity.

Ecological importance of Indian Pangolin

The Indian pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) is a major agent of ecosystem balance because they have very high specialization as an eater of insect ants, termites, and more. They can greatly reduce the overall pests of spiders, termites, wasps, and other insect families that can threaten crops, trees, and other vegetation, by feeding on them in massive numbers (Nadeem et al., 2015; Mahmood et al., 2021). The regulation of these pests not only reduces agricultural yield losses but also sustains forest health. By the tips of their claws, pangolins rip up the soil to search for ants and termites. Meanwhile, this digging process aerates the soil (Panda et al., 2010), allowing water to infiltrate the soil more effectively, nutrient distribution to be more rapid, and root growth to be more vigorous (Panaino, 2017; Maurice et al., 2019). The burrows further allow organic matter to link well with soil to ensure fertility and trigger

healthier plant growth. The burrows made by the pangolins are homes for other fauna such as rodents, reptiles, and insects as well. The secondary occupants are dependent on the empty pangolin homes for predators' avoidance, shelter from any weather extremity, and for nesting, thereby biodiversity is both preserved and it flourishes (WWF India, 2023). As food for larger predators such as leopards and jackals, these pangolins are parts of the food web and provide food for these animals. This dimension is a prerequisite for the interactions between predators and prey in their habitats. In the face of habitat disturbances and pollution, the presence or absence of Indian pangolins may act as an indicator of environmental health. Their declining presence is often associated with the degradation of ecosystems which may be traced to deforestation, soil erosion, and loss of biodiversity (Maurice et al., 2019).

Uncovering the myth: Pangolin body parts in traditional medicine

The use of pangolin body parts, including scales, skin, and bones, in traditional medicine is a widespread practice in Asia, particularly in China, Korea, Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Vietnam. This practice is rooted in superstition and cultural perception, rather than scientific evidence (Irshad et al., 2015; Karawita et al., 2018). Despite the lack of proof, pangolin scales are used to treat a range of ailments, including aphrodisiac effects, nervousness, hysteria, malaria, deafness, rheumatism, infertility, menstrual pain, and stomach disorders (Panda et al., 2010; Karawita et al., 2018; Irshad et al., 2015; Boakye et al., 2015). However, the strength of the evidence for the successful treatment of various health problems by these materials is very low. These traditional practices are largely based on the cultural perception of their usefulness, which is inconsistent with the proof of effectiveness. Pangolins are hunted in local areas of India for protein and traditional medicine. The high demand from China and Vietnam, for instance, significantly impacts the thriving international black market for pangolin meat and scales (Soewu and Adekanola, 2011). The primary reason behind this trade is the belief in Eastern and Southeast Asian countries that pangolin parts are not only a source of traditional Chinese medicine but also a unique delicacy. Although pangolin meat is occasionally consumed, the belief that its scales have medicinal properties poses the greatest threat (Pattnaik, 2008). These beliefs have spurred illegal trade networks, leading to the overexploitation of pangolins across Asia and Africa (Sexton et al., 2021). Authors of present study discourage the use of body parts as medicinal agents and appeal to create same for conservation of this unique and beautiful species.

Threats and conservation

The Indian pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) faces several threats due to illegal wildlife trade, habitat loss, and lack of public awareness, making conservation crucial to prevent its extinction (Mahmood et al., 2012; Mohapatra et al., 2015; Lyngdoh et al., 2020). Some observed threats and conservations efforts are discussed below.

1. **Poaching and illegal trade:** Indian pangolins are heavily trafficked for their scales which are considered to have therapeutic qualities in folk medicine in Asia, especially in China and Southeast Asia. Though it is being protected by CITES (Convention on International Trade in

Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora) and listed in Schedule I of India's Wildlife Protection Act, illegal poaching is still a major problem.

2. **Habitat destruction:** Rapid urbanization, deforestation, and agricultural expansion in India and other parts of its range are reducing the natural habitats of the Indian pangolin. This loss of habitat disturbs their food sources, mainly ants and termites, and their natural burrowing behaviour, which is the keystone to their survival.
3. **Low reproductive rate:** Indian pangolins have a low reproductive rate, normally one offspring is produced at a time. This poor inborn reproduction delimits the population recovery if masses are eliminated through poaching.
4. **Lack of foods:** Pangolins usually consume different types of ants and termites. The population of ants and termites are reducing very fast.

Conservation efforts

- a. **Legal protection:** The Indian pangolins are one of the species covered under Schedule I of the Wildlife Protection Act in India, which provides them with the highest protection. This act proscribes the hunting, trade, and exploitation of the animals. Even so, the authorities fail to curb those activities because of the huge demand for these animals and their products.
- b. **Habitat conservation:** Several initiatives should be there based on the preservation of forests and the creation of protected zones for the support of the pangolin population in those areas. Besides the benefit of the pangolin, it is also useful for the increment of the number of other species in the forest ecosystems.
- c. **Community awareness programs:** Government and Non-Government organizations, play an important role in informing the local public about the dangers of poaching and in teaching them about conservation, which involves the local people in monitoring and carrying out the poaching, getting away from these activities and move to an alternative.
- d. **Research and monitoring:** Research has been encouraged by biologists using recent technologies like radio telemetry to track the movements of pangolins and to identify their preferred habitats, their behaviours, and their habitat preferences. The information is very important for determining the appropriate protection arrangements for the species and for understanding their function in ecosystems.

Conclusion

Rising demand for pangolin scales Indian pangolin populations have reached to endangered category due to the scales of pangolins being illegally farmed and the sale of the species all around the world. Conservation efforts must address not only illegal poaching but also the deep-rooted cultural beliefs surrounding the medicinal use of pangolin parts. Increasing awareness of the lack of scientific support for these uses, coupled with stricter enforcement of wildlife protection laws, is essential for protecting this unique and ecologically valuable species. The survival of the Indian pangolin depends on a multi-faceted approach that combines strict law enforcement, habitat conservation, research, and community-

based programs. Public awareness and reducing demand for pangolin-derived products are equally critical in curbing illegal trade and ensuring the long-term survival of this unique species.

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